

مولانا عبید اللہ سندھی کا امروت (سندھ) میں قیام اور ان کی اسلامی علوم میں خدمات کا جائزہ

REVIEW OF MAULANA UBAIDULLAH SINDHI STAY IN AMRUT (SINDH) AND HIS CONTRIBUTION TO ISLAMIC EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article deals regarding Muhammad Bin Qasim's invasion on Sindh and its impact on Sindh's culture, education system and living style. It also briefly tells about early life of Maulana Ubaid Ullah Sindhi that he was born in Sikh family and got education in Sialkot, then impressed by the teachings of Islam and embraced Islam.

This article also tells about from where Maulana Ubaid Ullah Sindhi received his religious education and who were his teachers and mentors in this field. In this article, the marriage of Maulana Ubaid Ullah Sindhi is also discussed and his offspring's were also mentioned in short.

The major part of this article is about the services of Maulana Ubaid Ullah Sindhi which he rendered for publication and projection of Islamic studies during his stay at Amrot (Sindh). During his stay at Amrot (Sindh), he established a religious institution on pattern of Deobund as he was greatly influenced by Deobund School of thoughts. At this institution hundreds of religious scholars were taught and trained as well. Later, these scholars played an important role in promotion and projection of Islamic studies across the sub-continent. During his stay at Amrot (Sindh), Maulana Ubaid Ullah Sindhi also wrote many books and he also prepared a team of scholars for the purpose. This article is an effort to highlight the important role and services of Maulana Ubaid Ullah Sindhi, staying at Amrot Sindh, for the cause of Islam.

Keywords: Maulana Ubaid Ullah Sindhi, Amrot, Sindh, freedom fighter.

کلیدی الفاظ: مولانا عبید اللہ سندھی، امروت، سندھ، اسلامی علوم، تحریک آزادی۔

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